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Abstract: This study examines two Qur’ānic concepts expressed through the root *kh-t-m*, “the seal of the prophets” and disbelievers “having seals on their hearts and hearing” in light of pre-Islamic Christian and particularly Syriac literature. It suggests that both concepts entered the Qur’ān via the Syriac cognate of *kh-t-m*, *ḥ-t-m*, albeit in different ways: whereas Syriac interpretations of Isaiah 8:16, Daniel 9:24, Matthew 5:17–18, and Luke 24:44, found in the Diatessaron, the Peshitta, and works of Syriac theologians, informed the Qur’ānic conception of “the seal of the prophets,” it was the Syro-Hexapla, which inspired the concept of disbelievers being sealed, by adopting a minority rendering of Isaiah 8:16 from the Septuagint. The study then proposes that the Qur’ānic notion of “sealing the prophets” has a legal dimension, and that the Qur’ān positions Muḥammad as the great law-giver prophet, ending the line of the prophets who are the recipients of God’s covenants and “laws.” Muḥammad taking on such a role provides him a position comparable to Jesus’s role in the Syriac texts. Moreover, the study demonstrates that discussion of disbelievers “having seals on their hearts and hearing” with the Biblical precursor of disbelievers being sealed fits neatly into the broader context of the Qur’ān, when several phrases with Biblical antecedents become a part of the Qur’ānic discourse.

Keywords: Qur’ān, Isaiah 8:16, Syriac, seal of the prophets, seals on hearts and hearing, the root *kh-t-m*

Introduction

The present study analyzes two alternative meanings of the root *kh-t-m*: (1) the Qur'ānic phrase “the seal of the prophets” (*khātam al-nabiyyīn* in Q 33:40), which has positive connotations, and (2) the expression describing the sealing of the hearts and hearing of disbelievers (*khatama 'alā qalb/qulūb- wa-sam'* in Q 2:7; 6:46; 42:24; 45:23), which has negative connotations, in light of pre-Islamic Christian and particularly, Syriac literature.¹ This study demonstrates that both the positive and negative occurrences of sealing share the notion of closing – closing the line of the prophets and closing the disbelievers' hearts and ears. I will suggest that the use of sealing in Christian and especially, Syriac texts further elucidate implications of the Qur'ānic usages of sealing and the Christian background of those usages, relevant to historical-critical scholarship of the Qur'ān.

Although scholars have searched for similar usages of sealing in pre-Islamic Latin,² Greek

¹ All translations from Syriac, Hebrew, Greek, Armenian, and Georgian are mine unless indicated otherwise. The transliterations of Greek and Hebrew follow the 17th edition of the *Chicago Manual of Style* and the *SBL Handbook of Style* (2014) respectively. The transliteration of Syriac predominantly follows the East Syrian pronunciation as this pronunciation is more conservative and closer to Syriac prior to the emergence of West and East Syrian dialects. Yet *-aw* instead of the usual East Syriac vocalization *-āw* is used, and the double consonants are always indicated. By contrast, *begatkepat* spirantization is not indicated, and /u/ and /i/ are never marked as long vowels. Qur'ānic passages are transliterated with full vowels and pausal verse-endings throughout this study. The translation of the Qur'ān cited in this study belongs to Ali Quli Qarai and is adopted from REYNOLDS 2018, with my occasional revisions. While I capitalize God and all references related to Him, all other references to Muḥammad and Jesus are lowercased. Muḥammad is referred to as the prophet instead of the Prophet Muḥammad and Jesus as “he” and “the one who...” instead of “He” and “the One who...”

² Carsten COLPE highlighted a link between Daniel 9:24 and Christ, noting that Christ was viewed as the one sealing “vision and prophet” by the Latin theologian, Tertullian (160–240). COLPE 1984–1986, 76–79.

Christian,³ Manichaean,⁴ and Samaritan⁵ works and sought to read *khātam* in the phrase *khātam al-nabiyyīn*, which designates the prophet Muḥammad, against the background of *kh-t-m*'s Semitic cognates,⁶ they have only briefly referenced Syriac texts. Scholars have debated whether *khātam al-nabiyyīn* denotes the confirmation of the previous prophets, the finality of Muḥammad's prophecy, or both.⁷ To find support for the Christian understanding of Moses and

³ Uri RUBIN drew on a variety of sources to build his argument that the phrases “sealing” of “vision and prophet” in Daniel 9:24 are Biblical precursors to the Qur’anic phrase, “the seal of the prophets.” RUBIN briefly referenced the Greek Christian theologians Clement of Alexandria (d. ca. 215) and Athanasius of Alexandria (d. 373) as well. RUBIN 2014, 92. Nicolai SINAI added new evidence from two Greek theologians, John Chrysostom (d. 407) and Theodoret of Cyrus (393–457), both applying Daniel 9:24 to Jesus and interpreting “sealing” as “fulfilling and closing off [...] the succession of prophets who foretold his appearance.” SINAI 2023, 253–254.

⁴ Gedaliahu G. STROUMSA proposed that the Qur’anic “seal of the prophets” should be understood against the Manichaean background, given that, according to Muslim exegetes, Manichaeans considered Mani to be “the seal of the prophets.” STROUMSA 1986, 61–74. SINAI challenged STROUMSA’s hypothesis, arguing that Manichaeans may have retrojected the Qur’anic term to Mani. SINAI 2023, 253. Analyzing relations between Manichaeism and Islam, François DE BLOIS considers the “seal” as inherent to Manichaeism and argues that the use of the “seal” in the *Cologne Mani Codex* suggests that both Manichaeism and Islam borrowed the concept of sealing from Judeo-Christian tradition. He cites a phrase from the codex that employs the “seal” and reads as follows: “His [a prophet’s] disciples became the seal (*sphragis*) of his [a prophet’s] apostleship.” DE BLOIS 2004, 46. DE BLOIS might be right that Manichaeism borrowed the concept of sealing from Judeo-Christian tradition, yet one should underscore that sealing a prophet’s apostleship by his disciples is not the same as sealing the previous prophets and being the seal of the prophets. This use of sealing in the *Mani Codex* does not prove, in my view, that the phrase “seal of the prophets” was indeed prevalent in Manichaeism. For SINAI’s arguments against DE BLOIS’s suggestion, see SINAI 2023, 253, n 12.

⁵ According to Jarl FOSSUM, a Samaritan text references Moses as “the seal of the prophets.” FOSSUM 1993, 149–167. Still, due to the uncertain dating of this Samaritan text, SINAI has called for caution in treating it as a linguistic precedent for the Qur’ān. SINAI 2023, 253. For completing the prophecy in Judaism and absence of the word “sealing” in key passages, see COOK 2011.

⁶ Analyzing *khātam*, Arthur JEFFERY noted that the Arabic form *fā‘al* is irregular, and *khātam* must therefore be a borrowed from pre-Islamic Aramaic. Pointing to Syriac *hātmā* in 1 Corinthians 9:2, JEFFERY further asserted that the Targumic *hatîmā* and Christian Palestinian *hātimā* denoting “*obsignatio, finis, conclusio, clausula*” had meanings closer to how *khātam* is used in the Qur’ān. JEFFERY 1938, 120–121. The apostle Paul says in 1 Corinthians 9:2: “Even though I may not be an apostle to others, surely, I am to you! For you are the seal of my apostleship in the Lord.” The Peshitta renders “the seal of my apostleship” as *hātmā da-šlihut*. On the “seal of the apostleship,” see SINAI’s comment, who convincingly reasons against its influence on the Qur’ān. SINAI 2023, 253n12.

⁷ Addressing various Qur’anic verses, David POWERS declared that the Qur’anic concept of the finality of prophecy prevailed by the end of the first century AH. POWERS maintains that the Qur’ān was revised to support the idea of Muḥammad being the final prophet. POWERS 2009, 54, 151, and 226 and POWERS 2020, 333–408. In contrast,

Jesus as two great prophets and Jesus as the seal of the prophets comparable with Muḥammad, Hartmut BOBZIN concisely referred to the early Syriac theologian Aphrahat (d. shortly after 345). Yet, BOBZIN did not directly cite passages from Aphrahat’s *Demonstrations*.⁸ Subsequently, while Uri RUBIN helpfully cited Aphrahat’s two short comments on “sealing” of “vision and prophet” in Daniel 9:24 in order to underscore the passages intertwined notions of confirmation and finality,⁹ none of the lines cited by RUBIN used “seal” in Syriac.

Thus, the first part of this study focuses on the Qur’ānic term *khātām al-nabiyyīn* and its Syriac intertexts with the aim of demonstrating that the Syriac intertexts deserve a closer look. I propose that the concept of *khātām al-nabiyyīn* may have entered the Qur’ān via a Syriac geographically and linguistically proximate to the Qur’ānic milieu. The antecedent of *khātām al-nabiyyīn* might have been the Syriac use of the root *ḥ-t-m*, designating Jesus the final law-giver prophet who confirms and stands in line with other prophets and seals all prophecies. Moreover, I will show that Syriac exegetes adopted the root *ḥ-t-m* not from Daniel 9:24 – the Syriac translations of Daniel 9:24 do not use the root *ḥ-t-m* at all – but from Isaiah 8:16. It was the Peshitta’s (a Syriac translation of the Bible from Hebrew)¹⁰ rendering of Isaiah 8:16 “Bind up the testimony and seal the law” that some Syriac exegetes adopted as a descriptor of Jesus. Isaiah 8:16 alongside Daniel 9:24 and several New Testament verses, including Matthew 5:17–

Hartmut BOBZIN understands Muḥammad as Moses’s successor arguing that the idea of Muḥammad being Moses’s successor is deeply inherent to the Qur’ān. He suggested that *khātām al-nabiyyīn* must be understood as referring to the one who completes Moses’s work. For BOBZIN, just as Christianity presented Jesus as a prophet who confirmed and completed Moses’s prophecy, the Qur’ān presented Muḥammad as a figure with a similar purpose, stripping Jesus of the exalted status endowed on him by Christianity. BOBZIN 2010, 565–581. Uri RUBIN also underscored that the Qur’ān indeed regarded Muḥammad as the prophet who confirms the previous revelations. Eventually, RUBIN argued that the Qur’ān provides ample evidence for the idea of finality. RUBIN 2014, 66, 74.

⁸ BOBZIN 2010, 566.

⁹ RUBIN cites the following lines from Aphrahat’s *Demonstration* 19, chapter 11: “Now understand that after these weeks, the Messiah came and was killed in fulfillment of the vision and the prophets” and “Understand, my beloved, and perceive, that the weeks were fulfilled; the visions and the prophets have ceased. Sovereignty has been cut off from Judah.” RUBIN 2014, 92. Although RUBIN is right to assert that these lines convey the idea of confirmation and finality, none of these lines use “seal” in Syriac, rather they employ “for fulfillment” (*l-šulām*) and “[the visions and the prophets] ceased” (*qta* ܩܬܐ). For the Syriac text, see Parisot 1894, 885.

¹⁰ Sebastian BROCK notes that while it is uncertain when the Peshitta Old Testament was translated into Syriac, it seems likely that most books of the Peshitta Old Testament originate from between the second and early third century. BROCK 2006, 17 and 20.

18, Matthew 11:13, and Luke 24:44,¹¹ establish the basis for interpreting Jesus as the seal of the law and the one who ends vision(s) and prophets. I consequently probe discussion of sealing the law and all prophecies in the Peshitta, the Syro-Hexapla,¹² and the works of the most important Syriac theologians,¹³ Aphrahat (who has more relevant comments to offer), Jacob of Sarug (d. 521), and Narsai (d. ca. 500) in order to demonstrate palpable similarities between the Qur’ānic and Syriac understandings of the “seal of the prophets” and “seal of the law and the prophecies.”

Since scholars have been unable to identify pre-Islamic precursors to the Qur’ān’s discussion of the sealing of disbelievers’ hearts and ears which use the word “sealing” similarly,¹⁴ and while Muslim exegetes have compared sealing the hearts and ears with sealing

¹¹ The Old Syriac New Testament and the Peshitta New Testament originate from ca. third century and ca. 400 respectively. BROCK 2006, 20.

¹² Marketta LILJESTRÖM maintains that the Syro-Hexapla is the best witness to the Greek text of Origen’s fifth column and offers a literal translation from Greek. As LILJESTRÖM writes, “While the Syrohexapla is repeatedly introduced rather simplistically as a Syriac translation of the fifth column, the so-called LXX column, of Origen’s Hexapla, the translation was not made from the original work. In the course of time scholarly interpretation of the information has shifted towards the idea of the Syrohexapla’s *Vorlagen* being different kinds of copies of the LXX column of the Hexapla, along with collation of marginal readings. This coincides with what the colophons say, as well as contemporary descriptions.” LILJESTRÖM 2021, 660–661 and 655. Most parts of the Syro-Hexapla seem to be a Syriac translation of the Hexaplaric edition of the Septuagint prepared in Alexandria between 614–617, but R. G. JENKINS has demonstrated that the Syro-Hexapla of Isaiah might be a revision based on the Philoxenian Old Testament (early-sixth century) rather than a new translation straight from Greek. JENKINS 1989, 199–204; LILJESTRÖM 2021, 659 and 662. A revision or not, the Book of Isaiah as well as the Book of Daniel were prepared in January 617 according to the colophons. The colophons also reveal that the Patriarch Athanasius commissioned the translation that was carried out by Paul of Tella and his co-translators. The translation took place in the Monastery of the Antonines at the Enaton, an active monastic region, nine miles from Alexandria. Ibid.; VÖÖBUS 1971, 36–44. The Syro-Hexapla was widely used in the Syrian Orthodox Church, whereas the Peshitta was used in the Church of the East until the ninth century. BROCK 2006, 28–29; ROMENY 2006, 310. In a ninth-century letter, the Catholicos of the Church of the East, Timothy I (727/8–823) wrote about the Syro-Hexapla a hundred years after its production and made the version available to the East Syrian. LILJESTRÖM 2021, 658.

¹³ While I looked closely at the works of Ephrem the Syrian (d. 373), I was not able to find “sealing the prophecies,” “sealing the prophets,” or the concept of the sealed disbelievers.

¹⁴ Gabriel S. REYNOLDS pointed to a comparable discussion of sealing in Isaiah 6:9–10 and Exodus 4:21. REYNOLDS 2018, 32 and 268–269. Isaiah 6:9 reads as follows: “Go and say to this people: ‘Hear, but do not comprehend; see but do not understand. Make the heart of this people fat, and make their ears heavy, and blind their eyes, so that they may not see with their eyes, and hear with their ears, and comprehend with their hearts, and turn and be healed.’” The Hebrew of Isaiah 6:10 employs *š-m-n* and the Syriac translations use *‘-b-i*, all meaning

a book and sealing a jar,¹⁵ the second part of my study explores *khatama* in the Christian context of describing the state of disbelievers in this world.¹⁶ The root *t-b-* ‘ although related to *kh-t-m* remains beyond the scope of this study, given that the Qur’ānic *t-b-* ‘ and its Hebrew and Syriac cognates require further analysis. I contend that it is again Isaiah 8:16 which informed the understanding of *khatama* in reference to the sealing of the disbelievers. Whereas some Syriac exegetes interpreted the Peshitta’s phrase, “Bind up the testimony and seal the law,” as referring to Jesus, the Syro-Hexapla as well as some pre-Islamic Christian exegetes – using the Greek translation of the Bible, the Septuagint – interpreted Isaiah 8:16 as, “Then, those will become known who are sealed in order not to learn the law.” I suggest that this interpretation of being sealed and thus not learning the law of God might have become part of the Qur’ānic vocabulary referring to disbelievers as being sealed based on the influence of Christian theologians who

“fattening of the hearts.” For further Biblical references, see also *ibid.* Exodus 4:21 reads: “And God said to Moses, ‘When you return to Egypt, see that you perform before Pharaoh all the marvels that I have put within your power. I, however, will stiffen his heart so that he will not let the people go.’” While the Hebrew text has *hāzaq* (“to be strong,” “to obstinate,” “to bind”) in Exodus 4:21, Exodus 14:17; Joshua 11:20 and *qāšā* (“to harden”) in Exodus 7:3, the Greek Septuagint has *sklērynō* (“to harden”) in Exodus 4:21, Exodus 7:3, Exodus 14:17, Romans 9:18, and *synantaō* (“to harden”) in Joshua 11:20. The Syriac Peshitta uses the following verbs: *‘šen* (“to be heavy, hard”) in Exodus 4:21; *qašši* in Exodus 7:3 and Romans 9:18; *‘abbi* (“to make heavy,” “to harden”) in Exodus 14:17; *ethayyal* (“to be strengthened,” “to be strong”) in Joshua 11:20. Exodus, Joshua, and Romans are not available in the extant Syro-Hexapla. Yet since the Septuagint does not utilize “to seal,” it is very likely that the Syro-Hexapla would not use it either. Nicolai SINAI also cited various verses on sealing of the hearts from the Hebrew Bible to demonstrate that Biblical and especially Christian sealing metaphors have exclusively positive connotations, and this Qur’ānic sealing metaphor is distinct from the Biblical sealing metaphors. SINAI 2023, 248–250. Adi Shiran is currently preparing an article on a possible connection between Isaiah 6:9–10 and the Qur’ānic verses which use *khatama* for disbelievers.

¹⁵ See e.g., al-Ṭabarī, *Jāmi‘ al-bayān* (2001), 1, 265.

¹⁶ The use of *khatama* as sealing the mouths of disbelievers in the hereafter remains beyond the scope of this study, since the extra-Qur’ānic evidence presented here only illuminates the use of sealing in this world, and the use of *khatama* in hell requires further investigation. The state of the disbelievers in hell as depicted in Q 36:65 (“Today We shall seal their mouths (*nakhtimu ‘alā afwāhim*), and their hands will speak to Us, and their feet will bear witness (*wa-tashhadu arjuluhum*) concerning what they used to earn”) is so distinct from other Qur’ānic depictions of the inhabitants of hell that it is likely that sealing of the mouths has a precursor in pre-Islamic Christian texts. The only cross-reference to Q 36:65 is the Medinan verse Q 24:24: “On the day when witness shall be given against them (*tashhadu ‘alayhim*) by their tongues (*alsinatuhum*), their hands and their feet (*wa-arjuluhum*) concerning what they used to do.” Still, the idea of sealing of disbelievers’ mouths is neatly embedded within the wider Meccan Qur’ānic context, in which those denying God’s words with their mouths in this world (e.g., Q 18:5; 36:15, 18, 47) are prevented from speaking in hell and those with sealed hearts in this world are punished with sealed mouths in the hereafter.

propagated a similar interpretation. More specifically, Syriac, and in particular Syriac's use of the root *ḥ-t-m* to describe sealed disbelievers, as witnessed in the Syro-Hexapla, may have been the avenue through which this meaning of *ḥ-t-m* entered the Qur'ān.

I also refer to the periods of revelation according to the Nöldekean relative chronology of the Qur'ān refined by Nicolai SINAI¹⁷ in order to maintain the relevance of the Syro-Hexaplaric Books of Isaiah and Daniel, dating at the latest to January 617, to the pertinent Qur'ānic verses. Moreover, I analyze the Qur'ānic phrase *khatama 'alā qalb/qulūb-wa-sam'* in light of the Greek¹⁸ and Armenian¹⁹ *Commentaries on the Prophet Isaiah* attributed to Basil of Caesaria (d. 379) and John Chrysostom (d. 407), since both commentaries support an understanding of being sealed or having sealed oneself.

The Qur'ān's conversation with the pre-Islamic Syriac literature seems here especially plausible, given that various derivatives of *kh-t-m*, such as *makhtūm*, *khawātim* (the plural of *khātim* or *khātam*),²⁰ and *khitām* occur in pre-Islamic Arabic poetry, although never in regard to sealing someone or the hearts and hearing. The form *khātam* and *khatama 'alā qalb-/qulūb-wa-sam'* seem to be completely absent from pre-Islamic poetry.²¹

¹⁷ Nicolai SINAI proposes two divisions of the Meccan sūrah's and employs "early Meccan" and "later Meccan," thus eliminating "middle Meccan." His periodization is based on average mean verse length in transcription letters. In SINAI's refinement, the early Meccan period ends with Q 15 (mean verse length 43,12) and the later Meccan period begins with Q 50 (mean verse length 50,82). For further discussion of mean verse length, see SINAI 2017, 114–117.

¹⁸ The *Commentary on Isaiah* attributed to Basil of Caesaria originates from the fourth century. LIPATOV-CHICHERIN 2022, 132 and 146.

¹⁹ The Armenian translation of the *Commentary on the Prophet Isaiah* attributed to John Chrysostom dates from the fifth century. SMELOVA 2013, 299. SMELOVA makes a case in her article that this *Commentary on the Prophet Isaiah* is indeed composed by John Chrysostom. *Ibid.*, 295–310.

²⁰ Ibn Sīda, *al-Muḥkam wa-l-muḥīṭ al-a'zam* (2000), 5, 155–156.

²¹ For various derivatives of *kh-t-m*, see ARĀZĪ/MAṢĀLHA 1999, 409; al-Zawzanī, *Sharḥ al-qaṣā'id al-saba'* (2019), 323; Lyall 1913, 61; al-Mu'aybid 1965, 77; 'Abbās 1962, 119, 244, 314. My gratitude to Nadja Abuhussein and Raashid Goyal for drawing my attention to several verses of pre-Islamic Arabic poetry using the root *kh-t-m*. The root *kh-t-m* also appears in an Ancient South Arabian inscription. For *kh-t-m* translated as "to cultivate" in this Ancient South Arabian inscription, see ARBACH/SCHIETTECATTE 2012, 50–51.

***Khātam al-nabiyyīn* in the Qur’ānic Context and in Light of Its Syriac Intertexts**

***Khātam al-nabiyyīn* in the Qur’ānic Context**

To prove my hypothesis, the first chapter of this study briefly analyzes the Qur’ānic term *khātam al-nabiyyīn* and highlights Qur’ānic verses related to the status of Muḥammad. Both the phrase *khātam al-nabiyyīn*, as well as the noun *khātam* more generally, appear in the Qur’ān only once, as a designation of the prophet Muḥammad. Specifically, the phrase is used in Q 33, the Medinan sūrah exalting the status of Muḥammad.²² Q 33 presents Muḥammad as the receiver of a covenantal pledge (*mīthāq*), positioning him in the line of the other Qur’ānic prophets, Noah, Abraham, Moses, and Jesus (in v. 7), who have also received a covenantal pledge. Moreover, the sūrah emphasizes Muḥammad’s status as a prophet by referring to him repeatedly as *nabī* (in vv. 1, 28, 30, 32, 38, 45, 50, 53, 56, 59). Q 33:7 and 40 read as follows:

7: [Recall] when We took a covenantal pledge from the prophets (*akhadhnā mina l-nabiyyīna mīthāqahum*) and from you and from Noah and Abraham and Moses and Jesus the son of Mary, and We took from them a solemn covenantal pledge (*wa-minka wa-min nūḥin wa-ibrāhīma wa-mūsā wa-‘īsā bni maryama wa-akhadhnā minhum mīthāqan ghalīzā*).

40: Muḥammad is not the father of any man among you, but he is the apostle of God and the seal of the prophets (*wa-lakinna rasūla llāhi wa-khātama l-nabiyyīna*²³). God has knowledge of all things.

Read in tandem, these two verses depict Muḥammad as the seal of the previous prophets – Noah, Abraham, Moses, and Jesus – the prominent Biblical figures who forged the major covenants with God.²⁴ Muḥammad receives his covenantal pledge, after Jesus (e.g., *mīthāq*

²² SINAI 2017, 209.

²³ The variant readings of *khātam* confirm the use of the root *kh-t-m* and the meaning of sealing. Instead of *khātam*, al-Ṭabarī (d. 923) and al-Dānī (d. 1053) propose the active participle, *khātim al-nabiyyīn*, and the verb, *khatama l-nabiyyīn*, as variant readings. For *khātim*, see al-Ṭabarī, *Jāmi‘ al-bayān* (2001), 19, 122 and al-Dānī, *Kitāb al-taysīr* (1930), 179. For *khatama*, see also al-Ṭabarī, *Jāmi‘ al-bayān* (2001), 19, 122. Two other variant readings are attributed to ‘Abd Allāh Ibn Mas‘ūd (d. 652) and Ibn Khuthaym (d. ca. 682): *lakinna nabiyyan khatama* (“but [he] sealed the prophet”) and *lakinna nabiyyanā khatama* (“but our prophet sealed”). Al-Sharfī *et al.* 2016, 3, 271–272. Whereas “but our prophet sealed” supports the understanding of Muḥammad as the one who seals, “but [he] sealed the prophet” might imply the sealing of the prophet according to Daniel 9:24.

²⁴ For the covenants in the Qur’ān, see also ZELLENTIN, forthcoming. The Noahide covenant appears in Genesis 9:9–17, the Abrahamic covenant occurs in Genesis 17:2–21, the Mosaic covenant is recounted in Exodus 20:1–17, Exodus 24:6 and 8, and the “New Covenant” or “Testament” connected to Jesus is instituted during the Last Supper and the saying “this cup that is poured out for you is the new covenant in my blood” in e.g., Luke 22:20–22. The

indirectly in Q 5:14), Moses (e.g., *mīthāq* in 4:154, *‘ahida* in 7:134, and 43:49), and Abraham (*‘ahida* in 2:125). While Jesus, Moses, and Abraham are explicitly named as recipients of their covenants, as evidenced by the use of the words *‘ahd* and *mīthāq*, the words “covenant” and “covenantal pledge” do not appear anywhere in the Qur’ān in reference to Noah except for Q 33:7, whose covenant thus remains implicit. Muḥammad is also the prophet whom God mandates, together with Noah, Abraham, Moses, and Jesus, to maintain “religion,” and particularly, religious worship (*dīn*)²⁵ in the later Meccan verse Q 42:13 (mean verse length 99,57). All of these prophets share one universal commandment – maintaining the religion and avoiding sectarian division:

13: He has prescribed for you the religion which He had enjoined upon Noah and which We have [also] revealed to you (*shara ‘a lakum mina l-dīni mā waṣṣā bihi nūḥan wa-lladhī awḥaynā ilayka*), and which We had enjoined upon Abraham, Moses, and Jesus (*wa-mā waṣṣaynā bihi ibrahīma wa-mūsā wa-‘īsā*), declaring, “Maintain the religion, and do not be divided in it” (*an aqīmū l-dīna wa-lā tatafarraqū fīhi*). Hard on the associators is that to which you summon them. God chooses for it whomever He wishes, and He guides to it whomever returns penitently [to Him].

Muḥammad is not only positioned in the line of previous prophets who possessed the covenants, but is also described as confirming and testifying to the “previous messengers” (*ṣaddaqa l-mursalīn*) in the early Meccan verse Q 37:37 (mean verse length 31.20). The Qur’ān is introduced as the confirmation (*muṣaddiq*) of the previous revelations in the Medinan verses Q 2:89 and 97, with Muḥammad introduced specifically as the one who confirms them in v. 101. The Qur’ān includes direct and overt confirmation of the Gospel and the Torah (Q 3:3) and also features at least one passage, Q 21:105–106, confirming the validity of the Psalms (*zabūr*) revealed and given to the prophet David (Q 4:163 and 17:55).²⁶ Moreover, the late Meccan verse Q 7:157 fashions Muḥammad as the messenger and the prophet who had been prophesized in the Torah and the Evangelium. A similar theme of prophecy recurs in the Medinan verse Q 61:6, in which Jesus announces a future messenger named Aḥmad, a clear allusion to the name

Qur’ān seems to adopt the list of the covenants offered by the Syriac texts. Still, the appearance of these four prophets in the Qur’ān along with intra-Qur’ānic evidence regarding other Qur’ānic prophets, Aaron (e.g., Q 19:53 and 20:47, 26:16) and David (e.g., Q 6:84 and 89; 17:55), once again underscore that the priestly covenant with Aaron and the royal covenant with David are rejected in the Qur’ān.

²⁵ For rendering *dīn* as religious worship, see GOUDARZI 2023; For rendering *dīn* as “law” or “judgement,” see LINDSTEDT 2023.

²⁶ Q 21:105–106 reads as follows: “Certainly We wrote in the Psalms, after the reminder (*wa-la-qad katabnā fī l-zabūri min ba‘di l-dhikri anna l-arḍa yarithuhā ‘ibādiya l-ṣāliḥūn*): ‘My righteous servants shall indeed inherit the earth. There is indeed in this a proclamation for a devout people.’”

Muḥammad. The Qur'ān likewise establishes a legal parallel between Jesus and Muḥammad in Q 7:157, portraying Muḥammad as the one who relieves the believers of their loads and the fetters that were upon them, comparable to the role of Jesus in the third-century *Didascalia Apostolorum*.²⁷ The relevant part of Q 7:157 reads as follows:

157: Those who follow the apostle, the scriptureless²⁸ prophet, whose mention they find written with them in the Torah and the Evangelium (*alladhīna yattabi'ūna l-rasūla l-nabiyya l-ummiyya lladhī yajidūnahu maktūban 'indahum fī l-tawrāti wa-l-injīli*), who bids them to do what is right and forbids them from what is wrong, makes lawful to them all the good things and forbids them from all vicious things, and relieves them of their loads, and the fetters that were upon them (*wa-yada'u 'anhum iṣrahum wa-l-aghāla llatī kānat 'alayhim*). [...]

Muḥammad's status as the confirmer of the previous revelations is underscored in the aforementioned verses. While other prophets and holy scriptures also declare the arrival of Muḥammad, Muḥammad and the Qur'ān do not announce any other prophet to come. The absence of a novel prophecy and Muḥammad's and the Qur'ān's silence regarding it implies that Muḥammad is positioned as the final prophet. I derive this conclusion of Muḥammad's finality from a similar presentation of Jesus: Christ does not announce a prophet after him in the gospels, which Christians commonly understood in salvation history as indicative of the fact that Jesus had closed the line of the prophets who possessed the covenants and "laws." As I will discuss in the next chapter, an understanding of *khātam al-nabiyyīn* as the reference to continuity with and confirmation of previous prophecies and finality of Muḥammad's prophecy is widely supported by the Syriac intertexts, portraying Jesus in the similar manner.

Isaiah 8:16, Daniel 9:24, Matthew 5:17–18, Luke 24:44, and Their Interpretations as Syriac Intertexts of *Khātam al-nabiyyīn*

Biblical verses such as Isaiah 7:14, Isaiah 8:16, Daniel 9:24, Matthew 5:17–18, Matthew 11:13, Luke 24:27, and Luke 24:44 (see below) indicate explicitly or implicitly that, for pre-Islamic Syriac theologians, Jesus was the prophet²⁹ who sealed previous prophecies and the line of the

²⁷ For the portrayal of Jesus as the one who loosens the bonds of the law and a discussion of this portrayal's parallel in Q 7:157, see WITZTUM 2011, 275–277 and ZELLENTIN 2013, 139, 157–159.

²⁸ The translation of *ummī* as "scriptureless, not hitherto endowed with a scriptural revelation" follows here Nicolai SINAI's rendering in his entry on *ummī*. See SINAI 2023, 94–99.

²⁹ Jesus is addressed as the prophet in e.g., Matthew 13:57 ("And they took offense at him. But Jesus said to them, 'Prophets are not without honor except in their own hometown and in their own house.'"); Hebrews 1:1–2 ("Long

prophets.³⁰ I will focus specifically on Isaiah 8:16, Daniel 9:24, Matthew 5:17–18, and Luke 24:44 and the use of sealing in the context of these Biblical verses. This selection of verses and their interpretations by Syriac theologians proves particularly helpful for understanding the Qur’ānic usage of *khātām al-nabiyyīn*. While the exact Qur’ānic phrasing “the seal of the prophets” is absent from the Syriac texts, these texts are nonetheless replete with discussion of “sealing all prophecies” and Mosaic Law. Moreover, the texts invoke sealing in the context of describing prophets possessing the covenants and “laws.” The relevant Biblical verses read as follows:

Relevant Biblical passages	Peshitta	Syro-Hexapla
Daniel 9:24	Seventy weeks have been imposed upon your people and your holy city, for sin to be ended (<i>l-mešlam</i>) and transgressions to be finished (<i>l-megmar</i>); and to forgive iniquities and to bring in everlasting righteousness, the vision and prophets to be ended (<i>wa-l-mešlam ḥezwā wa-nbiyē</i>) and for the anointed one, (<i>w-la-mšihā</i>) the most holy. ³¹	Seventy weeks have been imposed upon the people of yours and the entire city, Sion, for sin to come to an end (<i>l-mešallāmu</i>) and to diminish (<i>l-me'zar</i>) the iniquity, and the iniquities to be complete (<i>wa-l-melyānā</i>) and to understand the vision (<i>wa-l-metbayyānu b-ḥezwā</i>) and to be given/to bring (<i>l-metyābu/l-maytāyu</i>) everlasting righteousness, and for the vision and the prophets/the prophecy (<i>ḥezwā wa-</i>

ago God spoke to our ancestors in many and various ways by the prophets, but in these last days he has spoken to us by a son, whom He appointed heir of all things, through whom He also created the worlds.”); Acts 3:22 (“Moses said, ‘The Lord your God will raise up for you from your own people a prophet like me. You must listen to whatever he tells you.’”).

³⁰ Prophets are mentioned after Jesus in the New Testament (e.g., Acts 15:32 and Acts 19:5–7), yet they are “lower-ranking functionaries who prophesy in the shadows of Jesus, John the Baptist, and the apostles. The early Christian prophets are presented as important figures with high authority, but not as towering figures. The Spirit speaks through them to give guidance to the church, but their prophetic utterances are not always considered incontestable. They are pneumatics who function in ways that are similar to the OT prophets, but their range of activities seems limited by comparison. Thus, it cannot be fairly said that they were considered true successors of the OT prophets.” COOK 2011, 119.

³¹ Gelston 1980, 35–36.

		<i>nbiyē/nbiyutā</i>) to come to an end (<i>l-meštallāmu</i>) and to rejoice/to anoint (<i>wa-l-mḥaddāyu/wa-l-memšah</i>) (for) the most holy. ³²
Isaiah 8:16	Bind up [Pl.] (<i>ṣur</i>) the testimony (<i>sāhdutā</i>) and seal [Pl.] (<i>wa-ḥtom</i>) the Law (<i>nāmosā</i>). ³³	(The translation follows here the Septuagint and is not relevant to the first part of the study)
Matthew 5:17–18	[Jesus said,] Think not that I am come to loosen the Law, or the Prophets (<i>nāmosā aw nbiyē</i>): I am not come to loosen, but to fulfill (<i>d-emallē</i>). “For truly I tell you, until heaven and earth disappear, not even one <i>yud</i> or a dash shall pass away from the Law until everything takes place (<i>d-koll nehwe</i>).” ³⁴	Nonexistent
Luke 24:44	He [Jesus] said to them, “This is what I told you while I was still with you: Everything must come to an end that is written about me (<i>neštallam koll meddem da-ktib</i>) in the Law of Moses, the Prophets,	Nonexistent

³² Ceriani 1874, 149r.

³³ In the Hebrew Bible, Isaiah 8:16 reads as follows: “Bind up (*ṣôr*) the message (*tə’ūdā*), seal (*ḥātôm*) the instruction (*tôrā*) with My disciples (*bəlimmūdāy*).” The Septuagint translates this verse differently and will be discussed in the second part of the study. In some editions of the Peshitta, Isaiah 8:16 ends after “seal the law.” The phrase “With my disciples” (*b-yawlāpnay*) begins the next verse, Isaiah 8:17. For ending Isaiah 8:16 with “seal the law,” see Lee 1823, 518; D-Bēt Qelāytā 1913, 394; *Biblia sacra juxta versionem simplicem quae dicitur Peshitta* 1888, 425. By contrast, the Leiden edition presents *b-yawlāpnay* as part of the verse 16. It seems to adjust v. 16 in line with the Hebrew original. Brock 1993, 15.

³⁴ Gwilliam/Pinkerton/Gwynn 1966, 5.

	and the Psalms (<i>b-nāmosā d-mušē w-ba-nbiyē wa-b-mazmorē</i>). ³⁵	
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As we can see, Isaiah 8:16 employs the phrase “to seal (*ḥtam*) the law” in the Peshitta, Daniel 9:24 refers to ending (*mešlam/meštallāmu*) “the vision and the prophets” (*ḥezwā wa-nbiyē*). This use of the plural – *nbiyē* – and “to end” instead of “to seal” stands in contradistinction to both the original Hebrew and the Greek translation of Daniel 9:24,³⁶ which speak of sealing “the vision and the prophet.” Both Syriac renderings found across the Peshitta and the Syro-Hexapla, *nbiye* and *mešlam/meštallāmu*, recontextualize Isaiah 8:16 and Daniel 9:24 from the Christian perspective, i.e., Christ, the anointed one (*mšihā*), ends (the line of) the prophets. The Syro-Hexapla moreover offers “prophecy” (*nbiyutā*) as a variant reading of “prophets” (*nbiyē*). This variant reading implies that Christ ends and fulfills the time of the prophecies. Christ also “seals” Mosaic law. Syriac theologians applied Isaiah 8:16 to Jesus despite the Peshitta’s rendering of the plural “bind up” and “seal.”³⁷ Finally, Matthew 5:17–18 and Luke 24:44 reaffirm that Christ fulfills everything what is written about him in Mosaic law,³⁸ the books of the Prophets, and the Psalms. Whereas Christ’s fulfilling of the Psalms is significant insofar as the Christian theologians read it as alluding to Jesus’s Messianic career (e.g., Psalm 40:6–8; 45:4), his Davidic heritage (e.g., Psalm 89 and Luke 3:31), and his status as eternal king (e.g., Psalm 110:1, 2, 4), Muḥammad only appears in the Torah and the Evangelium. It thus appears that the Qur’ān rejects Muḥammad’s status as the Messiah and instead emphasizes his status as law-giver and prophet.

³⁵ Gwilliam/Pinkerton/Gwynn 1966, 46.

³⁶ Daniel 9:24 in the Hebrew Bible reads as follows: “Seventy weeks have been decreed for your people and your holy city until the measure of transgression is filled and that of sin complete (*ūlāḥātēm*), until iniquity is expiated, and eternal righteousness ushered in; and vision (*ḥāzōn*) and the prophet (*wənābī*) sealed (*wəlaḥtōm*), and the Holy of Holies anointed (*wəlimšōah*).” The Septuagint translates Daniel 9:24 as follows: “Seventy weeks have been determined upon thy people, and upon the holy city, for sin to be ended, and to seal up (*sphragisai*) transgressions, and to blot out the iniquities, and to make atonement for iniquities, and to bring in everlasting righteousness, and to seal (*sphragisai*) the vision and the prophet (*prophētēn*), and to anoint (*chrisai*) the Most Holy.”

³⁷ As Roland L. TROXEL writes, the use of the plural is harmonized with 8:13, which also uses plural forms such as *qaddeš(w)*, *deḥlatkon*, *msay’ānkon*. TROXEL 2022, 185–186.

³⁸ On Christians’ understanding of Matthew 5:17 in Late Antiquity and Jesus’s role as the one who fulfills the law, see ZELLENTIN 2022, 205–243.

Adopting the wording of Matthew 5:17–18,³⁹ Aphrahat expresses this idea of Christ fulfilling the Law and the Prophets by sealing them in his *Demonstration II, On Love*:

The word that our Lord spoke is true: “The letter yud will not pass away from the Law (*men nāmosā*) or from the Prophets (*w-men nbiyē*),” since he has sealed (*htam*) them [...].⁴⁰

With his appearance, Christ seals the Law, i.e., Mosaic Law and the Prophets, i.e., the books of the Prophets. Aphrahat elaborates on Jesus’s role in fulfilling the Law and the Prophets in the same *Demonstration*, equating sealing with fulfilling without making a direct allusion to a specific Biblical verse invoking sealing:

And how were the Law (*nāmosā*) and the Prophets (*wa-nbiyē*) lacking and in need of being fulfilled? It was because the testament (*diatēqē*), which was the word of the promise, was hidden in them. For the testament which was given to Moses was not sealed (*mḥattmā*) until this last testament came, which was [also] before.⁴¹

And he [Jesus] brought an end (*w-baṭṭel*) to the visions and prophets (*ḥezwē wa-nbiyē*) among them [the Israelites] because they did not listen to the great prophet (*la-nbiyā rabbā*). The earlier testament was fulfilled (*etmalyat*) by the later one, and the works which are in the Law became old and outdated.⁴²

It is therefore Christ who seals the testament of Moses. By contrast, the testament of Christ is final and stands in continuity with the former testaments. Aphrahat’s understanding of the role of Jesus’s prophecy is underlined most clearly when Christ, the great prophet (*nbiyā rabbā*),⁴³ brings an end to the visions and prophets. For Aphrahat, the final generation (*dārā ḥrāyā*) emerged with the coming of Jesus. Aphrahat cites a list of the prophets who made covenants with God prior to the coming of the last prophet in his *Demonstration XI, On Circumcision*.

³⁹ Aphrahat seems to have mainly employed the *Diatessaron* (2nd century) and he may have had access to the Old Syriac gospels, while Aphrahat uses the Peshitta Old Testament. Lehto 2010, 19–21. One can reconstruct Matthew 5:17–18 in the Diatessaron based on Aphrahat’s and Ephrem the Syrian’s citations of the relevant verses in their works. ZELLENTIN cites several phrases which likely reflect the wording of the Diatessaron: “I have not come to loosen the Torah (*urāytā*) and the Prophets (*wa-nbiyē*) but to fulfill them,” “not one letter yud will pass away from the Torah and the Prophets until all takes place,” and “I have come to fulfill them.” ZELLENTIN 2022, 211–213.

⁴⁰ For the Syriac text, see Parisot 1894, 64; For an English translation, see Lehto 2010, 94.

⁴¹ For the Syriac text, see Parisot 1894, 57; For an English translation, see Lehto 2010, 91.

⁴² For the Syriac text, see Parisot 1894, 60; For an English translation, see Lehto 2010, 92–93.

⁴³ Luke 7:16 addresses Jesus as “a great prophet”: “Fear seized all of them, and they glorified God, saying, ‘A great prophet has risen among us!’ and ‘God has visited his people!’.” The Peshitta renders “a great prophet” in Luke 7:16 as *nbiyā rabbā*, analogous to the rendering adopted by Aphrahat. Luke 7:16 likely inspired Aphrahat to employ “the great prophet” in his *Demonstrations*. For *nbiyā rabbā*, see Gwilliam/Pinkerton/Gwynn 1966, 13.

This list looks very similar to the Qur'ānic list in Q 33:7, with emphasis placed on the law and the covenant:

In each case the law (*nāmosā*) and the covenant (*wa-qyāmā*) was changed (*ethallap*). First, God changed (*hallelp*) the covenant of Adam and gave another [one] to Noah. He also gave [one] to Abraham, but he changed that [one] and gave another [one] to Moses. When [the covenant] of Moses was not kept, he gave another [one] in the final generation (*b-dārā hrāyā*), a covenant that will not be changed. For Adam, the covenant involved not eating from the tree. For Noah, it was [represented by] the rainbow. [God] first chose Abraham because of his faith, and later [decreed] circumcision, a seal and a mark for his offspring. [The covenant] of Moses [is represented by] a lamb offered as a Passover sacrifice for the people. Not one of these covenants is like the next. [...] We know with certainty, my friend, that in each generation God establishes laws, and they function for as long as he pleases but then they are changed.⁴⁴

While the Qur'ānic list omits Adam, it otherwise hews closely to the list of prophets provided by both the Hebrew Bible and Aphrahat – Noah, Abraham, Moses, and Jesus. One could explain Adam's omission from the Qur'ānic list as based on the view that Adam forgot his covenant⁴⁵ and failed to keep God's commandment to refrain from eating from the tree. For Aphrahat as well, Adam is the only figure mentioned who did not keep the commandment and covenant and was thus condemned.⁴⁶ The Qur'ānic list thus includes only the prophets who keep God's commandment, with Muḥammad sealing this positive list. Moreover, God's command to Adam was limited to the Garden and Adam and Adam's spouse (e.g., Q 2:35; 7:19) and had no broader application. In contrast, the divine commandments given to the next four covenant recipients established laws that remained directly relevant to humanity. As discussed above, these covenants shared a core theological message: maintain the religion and avoid sectarian division (as stated in Q 42:13). This process of divine legislation reached its completion during Muḥammad's prophecy, when he received the fifth covenant, as expressed in Q 5:3: "Today, I [God] have perfected your religion" (*al-yawma akmaltu lakum dīnakum*). Unlike Christianity, which emphasizes a direct theological connection between Adam and Jesus Christ (who is viewed as the "second Adam" in 1 Corinthians 15:45–49), the Qur'ān does not establish such a parallel relationship between Adam and Muḥammad. This theological difference also helps to explain why Adam can be excluded from the Qur'ānic list of covenant recipients.

⁴⁴ For the Syriac text, see Parisot 1894, 497, 500; For an English translation, see Lehto 2010, 273. Aphrahat elaborates on each covenant and law given to these prophets in Parisot 1894, 473, 476 and Lehto 2010, 264–265.

⁴⁵ Adam forgot his covenant in Q 20:115: "Certainly We had enjoined Adam earlier, but he forgot, and We did not find any resoluteness in him" (*wa-la-qad 'ahidnā ilā ādama min qablu fa-nasiya wa-lam najid lahu 'azmā*). Cf. the use of the word "forget" below in Jacob of Sarug's Homily IV of *Against the Jews*.

⁴⁶ For the Syriac text, see Parisot 1894, 473 and 476; For an English translation, see Lehto 2010, 264–265.

Jacob of Sarug shares the same Syriac Christian list of prophets – Adam, Noah, Abraham, Moses, and Jesus – with whom God made the five covenants (*hemšā qyāmin*)⁴⁷ and to whom God gave five “books” of the law. In Homily IV of *Against the Jews*, Christ is placed at the end of this list, positioned as the one who accomplishes everything what was before and represents the fifth “book” of the law:

The law (*urāytā*) is composed of five books (*hemšā seprin*) but only one

was despised one day by the People [the Jews], forgotten (*t'āy*) as if it did not exist.

God had five covenants (*hemšā qyāmin*) with humanity,

but the son of the Hebrews does not know the fifth [covenant].

This is also the fifth (*d-hemšā*) [book], the book (*seprā*) he [the son of the Hebrews] forgot (*t'ā*). [...]

He commanded Adam not to eat from the tree (*pqad lēh ādām d-lā nekol-wā men ilānā*),

to Noah He taught killing [animals], then eating the meat [of animals] (*wa-l-nuḥ alpēh d-neqṭol besrā w-ken ekal lēh*).

to Abraham He gave circumcision, a clear sign (*l-abrāhām dēn yab lēh gzurtā rušmā gelyā*),

to Moses He revealed all hidden symbols of His creation (*wa-glā l-mušē rāzē kesyē d-bāruyutēh*).

After all these, He sent His son to fulfill everything (*w-bātar hālēn šaddar la-brēh da-nšamlē koll*).⁴⁸

Consistent with Aphrahat’s understanding, the idea of Jesus’s sealing the prophecy (*nbiyutā*) appears in Jacob of Sarug’s homilies. Jacob of Sarug deploys the word “prophecy” in reference

⁴⁷ Jacques de Saroug, *Homélie contre les Juifs* (1976), 120 (line 119). One should also bear in mind the significance of the number five. Elaborating on the five covenants, Jacob of Sarug relates the number five to the five senses (sight, smell, hearing, taste, and touch) perfecting the body and the Pentateuch (the five books of Moses). Jacques de Saroug, *Homélie contre les Juifs* (1976), 118–120 (lines 115–134). For the number five in numeric symbolism alluding to human life, the five senses, and love, see SCHIMMEL 1993, 105–121. Whereas the Qur’ān refers equally to the five prophets, it does not expand on the symbolical significance of five anywhere. I am grateful to Thomas Eich for alerting me to the significance of the number five.

⁴⁸ Jacques de Saroug, *Homélie contre les Juifs* (1976), 120 (lines 117–121) and 122 (lines 153–157). Jacob also writes: “Neither from Adam, nor from Noah, or from Abraham // Or Moses you [O, Jew] hold life, but it is from him [Jesus]. // It is about him that Moses wrote, in him Abraham was blessed, // by him that Noah, the righteous, was delivered from the flood // Do not hesitate any longer, because the son of God has delayed // through his crucifixion he came into the world, fulfilling all things (*da-nšamlē koll ba-zqīputēh*).” Jacques de Saroug, *Homélie contre les Juifs* (1976), 120 (lines 139–144).

to all previous prophecies, all previous prophets, or specifically Isaiah’s prophecy, depending on the context. Adopting the wording of Isaiah 8:16 in the Peshitta, Jacob of Sarug refers to the sealing Isaiah’s prophecy in his Homily I of *Against the Jews*:

The son of God has formed and sealed the prophecy (*ṣārāh w-ḥatmāh la-nbiyutā brēh d-alāhā*),

and Isaiah prophesied “bind up [sg.] the testimony!” (*āp eša ‘yā ṣūr sāhdutā metnabbē-wā*)

On the way of the prophecy our lord walked and came (*hallelk w-etā māran b-urḥā da-nbiyutā*).⁴⁹

A few lines earlier Jacob of Sarug also declares:

Our lord who has come to enforce the limit of prophecy (*māran d-etā labkēh l-sākāh da-nbiyutā*),

and he gave no sign that another [prophet] will come, since there is [will be] none (*w-lā yab ātā d-nētē ḥrēnā kad lā itaw*).⁵⁰

In these lines, the sealing of Isaiah’s prophecy alludes to the fulfilling and ending all prophecies and prophets. Jesus walks “the way of the prophecy,” i.e., in line with previous prophets who are typological representations of Christ, and in this line of typological reasoning, the prophetic career of every single prophet foreshadows Christ. The end of the prophecy is underscored by another phrase from Isaiah 8:16, namely, the “binding up the testimony.” Moreover, after mentioning the prophecies of David and Isaiah,⁵¹ Jacob clearly states that prophecy has been exhausted and that there will be no other prophet.

The motif of sealing as fulfilling and closing recurs in Jacob’s homilies. In his homily *on the Nativity*, Jacob first links sealing the Law⁵² with Isaiah 8:16 and the fulfilling of all Isaiah’s prophecies. Yet, he then refers to all the books of the prophecies which receive their seal through Christ:

⁴⁹ Jacques de Saroug, *Homélie contre les Juifs* (1976), 62 (lines 287–289).

⁵⁰ Jacques de Saroug, *Homélie contre les Juifs* (1976), 62 (lines 283–284). Two other lines also explicitly express the idea of the finality of Christ’s prophecy using *šlem*: “And because [Mary] has given birth, the story of prophecy is ended (*wa-d-yeldat lāh šlem lēh šarbā da-nbiyutēh*). From his story all the voices of prophecy have stayed quiet [ceased] ([...] *w-nāḥ men šarbēh kollhon qālē da-nbiyutā*).” Bedjan 2006, 6, 187.

⁵¹ Jacques de Saroug, *Homélie contre les Juifs* (1976), 62 (lines 270–282).

⁵² Jacob of Sarug also writes in his discussion of Christ’s epiphany that Christ perfects the Law. For Jacob, “the path of Mosaic Law” (*urḥā nāmosaytā d-bēt mušē*) was advanced to reveal the perfect teaching of Christ (*yulpānēh gmirā da-mšihā*). While the Law is initiated with Moses, it is completed with John the Baptist. After Christ’s baptism, Christ announces “the superior perfection of the Law” (*gmirutā da-l’el men nāmosā*). Jacques de Saroug, *Six homélie festales en prose* (1986), 550.

The mysteries and the parables and all the words of prophecy have been fulfilled (*rāzē w-matlē w-kollhēn mellē da-nbiyutā hway ba- 'bādā*);

O object of prophecy, seal the Law (*āw d-metnabbē ḥtom nāmosā*).

Bind up [sg.]⁵³ the testimony; do not prophesy, O seer (*ṣūr sāhdutā lā tetnabbē āw ḥazāyā*),

because prophecy has reached its limit in the son who has shone forth (*da-nbiyutā eḥdat sākāh ba-brā da-dnah*).⁵⁴

The virgin gave birth, everything that had been written was ended (*btultā yeldat wa-šlem kollhēn da-ktibān-way*).

It is becoming to you, my lord, to perfect the books of the prophecy (*yāyē lāk mār tegmor seprē da-nbiyutā*),

and that all the symbols of truths should be accomplished in you (*w-nethattmun bāk kollhon rāzē d-šarirātā*).⁵⁵

The use of the root *ḥ-t-m* and the verb *eḥattam* to denote accomplishing and ratifying also appear in Jacob of Sarug's other homilies:

The symbols of Moses, which were so numerous, were accomplished in him (*w-eḥattam bēh rāzay mušē d-saggiyin-waw*).⁵⁶

Each type of truth was accomplished (*w-eḥattam-wā kollēh ṭupsā d-šarirātā*).⁵⁷

Jacob considers Jesus a figure who ratified and fulfilled Moses's symbols and each type of truth. Similarly, Narsai speaks of ratification the anxious voices of prophecy in his second homily on *Epiphany*, evoking Matthew 11:13⁵⁸:

[...] because through his sacrifice he purifies the [sinful] stains of his fellow men.

⁵³ Jacob of Sarug uses the singular instead of the plural in the original Peshitta wording of Isaiah 8:16 and addresses the prophet Isaiah in the singular.

⁵⁴ For the Syriac text, see Kollamparmpil 2010, 205 (lines 163–166); For an English translation, *ibid.*, 204.

⁵⁵ For the Syriac text, see Kollamparmpil 2008, 49 (lines 387–388); For an English translation, see *ibid.*, 48. These lines invoke Luke 24:27: “And beginning with Moses (*men mušē*) and all the Prophets (*w-men kollhon nbiyē*), he explained to them what was said in all [the Scriptures] concerning himself.”

⁵⁶ Bedjan 2006, 3, 239.

⁵⁷ Bedjan 2006, 3, 231.

⁵⁸ Matthew 11:13 in the Peshitta indicates the end of all prophecies and law in Christ: “For all the Prophets and the Law (*nbiyē w-urāytā*) prophesied until John.”

[He is] also the one [whom John] named and called “the man who comes at the end” (*gabrā d-etā b-ḥartā*),

because at the consummation of the ages (*da-b-šulāmā d-zabnē*) he will appear (*dānaḥ*) and free all (*w-mḥarrar koll*).

For his sake, [John] became a harp for the Spirit of revelation,

so that in him there might be accomplished the anxious voices of prophecy (*d-bēh neḥattmun qālē šḥiqē da-nbiyutā*).⁵⁹

According to Narsai, Jesus is the one who appears at the end, and with his appearance, the prophecies and the voices of the prophets are ratified and terminated. In Homily II, *On the Divine Revelations to Patriarchs and Prophets*, Narsai suggests that Christ concludes the symbols, sets a seal on the revelations, and seals them until Christ’s Second Coming.⁶⁰ Narsai expresses the concepts of concluding and sealing as closing by using derivatives of *ḥ-t-m* and *t-b-‘*:

And He called “the anointed one” to be his name that comes to conclude the symbols (*wa-qrāy ba-šmēh mšihā d-ātē l-ḥutām rāzē*),

with his death, he showed that there is nothing again after his death (*b-mawtēh baddeq d-layt tub meddem bātar mawtēh*),

that he fulfills the anxious course of the prophecy (*da-mšamlē lēh l-raḥtā šḥiqā da-nbiyutā*).

The prophet of the Spirit cast a seal on the revelations (*tab ‘ā armi nbiyā d-ruḥā ‘al gelyānē*)

and sealed them so that they become secure until his shining forth (*w-ḥattem ennon d-nehwon ba-zhir ‘dammā l-denḥēh*).⁶¹

Narsai uses sealing in the context of the Second Coming of Christ, whereas sealing in regard to Muḥammad on the Day of Judgement is absent from the Qur’ān. Yet, in conclusion, when comparing the Qur’ānic and Syriac notions of sealing the prophets and the prophecies, it is striking that sealing and the derivatives of the root *ḥ-t-m* denote confirmation, fulfillment, and completion across both the Qur’an and the Syriac texts. Still, despite this conceptual similarity,

⁵⁹ For the Syriac text, see McLeod 1979, 84 (lines 220–224); For an English translation, see *ibid.*, 85.

⁶⁰ Sealing in reference to the second coming of Christ appears in Revelation 22:10: “Then he told me, ‘Do not seal up the words of prophecy in this book, because the time is near.’” It is reminiscent of Daniel 12:4: “But you, Daniel, shut up these words and seal the book until the time of the end. Many will roam to and fro, and knowledge will increase.”

⁶¹ Mingana, 1905, 1, 50.

the Syriac intertexts emphasize “sealing” of the books of the previous prophets including the sealing of Mosaic Law and “completing” the line of the prophets. On the contrary, the Qur’ān underscores “sealing” of the previous prophets. Nevertheless, the Syriac intertexts support the interpretation of *khātam al-nabiyyīn* as the seal of the law-giver prophets. When this expression is read alongside the list of the prophets mentioned in Q 33:7, Muḥammad is portrayed as the law-giver prophet, who confirms the previous prophets, who are recipients of the covenants, and completes the line of those prophets.

The Qur’ānic Disbelievers who have Seals on Their Hearts and Hearing and “Those who are Sealed in Order not to Learn the Law” of Isaiah 8:16

The Qur’ānic Disbelievers who have Seals on Their Hearts and Hearing

The verb *khatama* is used four times (Q 2:7; 6:46; 42:24; 45:23) in the Qur’ān in the context of sealing hearts or hearts and hearing of the disbelievers in this world. More specifically, *khatama* is employed as part of the rhetoric against the disbelieving contemporaries of the prophet Muḥammad, whose hearts and hearing God has sealed. By sealing their hearts and hearing, God has thereby prevented these disbelievers from hearing the Qur’ān and perceiving and understanding it with their hearts.⁶² Disbelievers’ having seals on the hearts and hearing also explains why, in Qur’ānic discourse, disbelievers never recognize God’s signs or Muḥammad’s warnings.⁶³ To better explicate these negative connotations of sealing, I juxtapose the relevant verses against their periods of revelation. Based on average mean verse length, the chronologically earliest of these verses is Q 45:23:

Period of revelation	Relevant verse
Later Meccan (mean verse length 84)	Q 45:23: Have you seen him who has taken his desire as his god, whom God has knowingly led astray, and set a seal upon his hearing and his heart (<i>wa-khatama ‘alā sam‘ihi wa-qalbihi</i>), and

⁶² Regarding the heart’s role as a center of both cognitive understanding and spiritual perception, where religious insights are processed and understood, see SEIDENSTICKER 1992 and SINAI 2023, 578–587.

⁶³ Q 2:6 for example underscores the uselessness of warning: “As for the repudiators, it is the same to them whether you warn them or do not warn them, they will not have faith (*inna lladhīna kafarū sawā’un ‘alayhim a-andhartahum am lam tundhirhum lā yu’minūn*).”

	put a covering on his sight? So who will guide him after God? Will you not then take heed?
Later Meccan (mean verse length 99.57)	Q 42:24: Do they say, “He has fabricated a lie against God?” If so, should God wish He would set a seal on your heart (<i>yakhtimu ‘alā qalbika</i>). God will efface the falsehood and confirm the truth with His words. He knows indeed well what is in the breasts.
Later Meccan (mean verse length 117.87)	Q 6:46: Say, “Tell me, should God take away your hearing and your sight and set a seal on your hearts (<i>wa-khatama ‘alā qulūbikum</i>), which god other than God can restore it for you?” Look, how We paraphrase the signs variously; nevertheless, they turn away.
Medinan (mean verse length 137.19)	Q 2:7: God has set a seal on their hearts and their hearing (<i>khatama llāhu ‘alā qulūbihim wa- ‘alā sam ‘ihim</i>), and there is a covering on their sight, and there is a great punishment for them.

The first use of the verb *khatama* to denote the state of disbelievers in this world can be found in the later Meccan Qur’ān. The later Meccan dating of the relevant sūrahs is significant because the pertinent Syriac intertexts may originate from approximately the same time, 617 CE (see footnote 25 and below). One could date these later Meccan and Medinan sealing metaphors definitively to after 614 CE and likely around or even after 617 CE, if one abides by Zishan GHAFFAR’s dating of the revelation of several pertinent later Meccan sūrahs to post 614 CE.⁶⁴

Considering that *khatama* is combined with various words denoting physical senses and that the verb is not always used in the same way across the Qur’ān (cf. “heart” in Q 6:46 and 42:24, “his hearing and his heart” in 45:23 and “their hearts and their hearing” in 2:7),⁶⁵ the Qur’ān seems to adopt the Christian notion of sealing, as shown below, and reshape it when discussing sealing in the context of hearts and hearing. Moreover, *khatama* is comparable with

⁶⁴ Zishan GHAFFAR argues that two later Meccan sūrahs – Q 19 (mean verse length 62.42) and 38 (mean verse length 51.98) – react to the conquest of Jerusalem by the Sassanians in 614 CE. If some later Meccan sūrahs originate after 614, the relevant later Meccan sūrahs might have emerged between 617 CE and before the *hijrah* in 622. GHAFFAR 2020, 12–13.

⁶⁵ The meaning of *khatama* has been always clear for the Muslim exegetes, as indicated by the fact that they do not provide any variant readings for *khatama* in Q 2:7, 6:46, 42:24, 45:23.

the verb *ṭabaʿa* (e.g., Q 7:100–101, 16:108). Both *khatama* and *ṭabaʿa* designate “to seal,” are employed similarly in regard to hearts, hearing, and sight (cf. *ṭabaʿa* in Q 16:108), and become part of the Qurʾānic revelation simultaneously in the later Meccan sūrahs.⁶⁶ While scholars have yet to unearth the Biblical precursor to *ṭabaʿa*, the use of the verb *khatama* to discuss disbelievers in this world is well embedded into the broader context of the Qurʾān. Several expressions invoking the impairing of senses, expressions which have Biblical precedents, are also first mentioned in the later Meccan sūrahs.⁶⁷

When the Qurʾān employs sealing metaphors, it is always God who sets a seal on hearts and hearing. If God seals the hearts of those (Q 6:46) who have hardened hearts (*qasat qulūbuhum* = “their hearts hardened” in v. 43), see their deeds as alluring (*wa-zayyana lahumu l-shayṭānu* = “Satan decked out fair to them [what they were doing]” in v. 43), and deny God’s signs (*wa-lladhīna kadhdhabū bi-āyātīnā* = “and those who deny Our signs” in v. 49), God is also the One to remove their seals (*man ilāhun ghayru llāhi yaʿtikum bihi* = “who is god other than God to give it back to you” in v. 46). God’s ability to both seal and remove the seals from

⁶⁶ *Ṭ-b-* appears only as a verbal form *ṭabaʿa* in later Meccan and Medinan sūrahs and occurs more frequently than *khatama*, in total eleven times. *Ṭabaʿa* also predominantly designates sealing the hearts, though it is used once to designate the sealing of hearing, hearts, and the sight (Q 16:108). *Ṭabaʿa* is mentioned in the Qurʾān at approximately the same time as *khatama*, as shown by the reconstruction of the time of revelation of the verses using *ṭabaʿa*: later Meccan: 7:100 and 101 (mean verse length 104.27); 10:74 (mean verse length 104.36); 16:108 (mean verse length 93.41); 30:59 (mean verse length 87.20); 40:35 (mean verse length 89.20); Medinan: Q 4:155; 9:87 and 98; 47:16; 63:3. *Khatama* might have first become part of the Qurʾān, followed closely *ṭabaʿa*, if one takes the mean verse length into account. In contrast to *khatama*, *ṭabaʿa* is employed widely in regard to repudiators (*kāfirūn* in e.g., Q 7:101), hypocrites (*munāfiqūn* in 63:1–3), the rich (9:93), and Jews (4:155), contemporaries of Muḥammad (e.g., 47:16), and contemporaries of the previous prophets (40:34–36). The members of each of these groups are characterized as those who do not understand, know, and listen, who follow their low desires, and on whose hearts, hearing, and sight God sets a seal (16:108).

⁶⁷ The phrase “We put coverings on their hearts” (*jaʿalnā ʿalā qulūbihim akinnatan*), which has a Biblical precedent in 2 Corinthians 3:15–16, first appears in Q 6:25, 17:46, and 18:57. All these verses are later Meccan, and their sūrahs have mean verse lengths of 117.87, 90.15, and 90.98 respectively. The expressions, “the hearts hardened” (*qasat qulūbuhum*) in Q 6:43 (117.87 mean verse length) and “those having hardened hearts” (*qāsiyat al-qulūb*) in 39:22 (98.40 mean verse length) also enter the later Meccan Qurʾān. For the Biblical precursors to hardening the hearts, see footnote 3. Q 43:40 (61.78 mean verse length) and 25:73 (75.25 mean verse length) are the first later Meccan verses, using the notion of blindness and disability of recognizing God’s signs with its Biblical antecedent in e.g., John 12:40. Finally, heaviness in the ears (*fī adhānihim waqrun*), with its Biblical precedent in e.g., Matthew 13:15 and Acts 28:26–27 (*b-ednayhon yaqirāit šmaʿ* and *mašmaʿthon awqar*) only occurs in the later Meccan verses, beginning with Q 17:46 (90.15 mean verse length). EL-BADAWI 2014, 126–128; REYNOLDS 2018, 439–440; SINAI 2023, 576–577.

disbelievers conveys God’s omnipotence. While, on its surface, God’s sealing on the hearts and hearing of the disbelievers has seemingly deterministic or predestinarian implications, scholars have convincingly argued that “sealing [...] follows prior misdeeds.”⁶⁸

One can further elucidate the intertwined nature of the impious behavior that results in God sealing the hearts and hearing of the disbelievers and the significance of the consequences that these disbelievers experience when their hearts and hearing are sealed from the context of the relevant sūrahs. Having a seal on a heart (Q 42:24) is the result of fabricating a lie against God (*iftarā ‘alā llāhi kadhiban* = “he has fabricated a lie against God” in v. 24) and not believing in the Hour (*inna lladhīna yumārūna fī l-sā‘ati la-fī ḍalālin ba‘īd* = “Indeed, those who are in doubt about the Hour are in extreme error” in v. 18). Whereas the disbelievers hear the words of the revelation (*yasma‘u āyāti llāhi tutlā ‘alayhi* = “hears the signs of God being recited to him” in Q 45:8) before God seals their hearts and hearing (v. 23), they persist arrogantly (*yuṣirru mustakbiran* = “persists arrogantly” in v. 8). They take God’s words with scorn (*ittakhadhahā huzuwan* = “he takes them in derision” in Q 45:9), deny His words (*wa-lladhīna kafarū bi-āyāti rabbihim* = “who deny the words of their Lord” in v. 11), and follow their low desires (*mani ttakhadha ilāhahu hawāhu* = “who has taken his desire as his god” in v. 23). Then, those who have a seal on their hearing and hearts (Q 45:23) believe only in the present life (*mā hiya illā ḥayātunā l-dunyā* = “there is nothing but the life of this world” in v. 24), argue with the prophet Muḥammad, and doubt the truth (*qālū ‘tū bi-ābā’inā in kuntum ṣādiqīn* = “they say, ‘Bring out fathers [back], if you are truthful’” in v. 25). While they hear the words of the revelation (*waidhā tutlā ‘alayhim āyātunā bayyinātin* = “when our clear signs are recited to them” in Q 45:25) and God’s promise (*wa‘d allāh* in v. 32), they are not convinced (*mā naḥnu bi-mustayqīnīn* = “we are not convinced” in v. 32). They have no knowledge (*mā lahum bi-dhālika min ‘ilmin* = “they do not have any knowledge of that” in v. 24) and particularly, no knowledge of the Hour (*mā nadrī mā l-sā‘atu* = “we do not know what the Hour is” in v. 32).

With a better understanding of sealing the disbelievers in mind, I turn next to sealing’s Christian precursors. These Christian texts employ the concept of sealing to depict a lack of perception and understanding of the law(s) and God’s words.

⁶⁸ For a good overview of and introduction to the arguments of Muslim and Western scholars against the predestinarian interpretation, see SINAI 2023, 250.

On an Interpretation of the Septuagint Translation of Isaiah 8:16 as the Christian Intertext of the Qur’ānic Disbelievers’ Sealing

I propose that the negative connotation of sealing in the Qur’ān originates from a very specific, less widespread interpretation of the Septuagint’s rendering of Isaiah 8:16. To prove my hypothesis, I first offer Isaiah 8:16’s Greek translation and a minority interpretation of Isaiah 8:16 found in the Syro-Hexapla. After discussing reasons for the specific phrasing of “being sealed” or “seal oneself” in Isaiah 8:16, I then explore two examples of this minority interpretation found in pre-Islamic Armenian and Greek Christian texts.

The Septuagint’s rendering of Isaiah 8:16 is remarkable for several reasons: First, the Septuagint renders only a part of the Hebrew Isaiah 8:16 – “seal (*ḥātôm*) the instruction (*tôrâ*) with My Disciples” – omitting the phrase “bind up the testimony.”⁶⁹ Second, the Septuagint renders “seal the instruction with My Disciples” interpretatively and not literally. Third, the Greek grammatical form of sealing and the word order in Greek potentially suggest three understandings of Isaiah 8:16: “to seal [the law],” “to be sealed, [the law...],” or “to seal oneself [, the law...].” All three of these possibilities are recognized in Christian texts⁷⁰ and highlighted below:

The Hebrew Isaiah 8:16	The Septuagint’s rendering of Isaiah 8:16	The Syro-Hexapla’s rendering of Isaiah 8:16
“[...] seal (<i>ḥātôm</i>) the instruction (<i>tôrâ</i>) with My disciples (<i>bālimmūdāy</i>).”	<i>Tote phaneroi esontai hoi sphragizomenoi/ esphragismenoi⁷¹ ton nomon tou mē mathein.</i>	Then, those will become known (<i>hāydēn idi ‘ē nehwun hālēn</i>) who are sealed/sealed with a seal (<i>d-methatmin/d-methatmin b-ḥātmā</i>)

⁶⁹ TROXEL 2008, 235–236. For an analysis of the translation of the “instruction” (*tôrâ*) as the “law” (*nomos*), see *ibid.*, 234–246; BLENKINSOPP 2019, 243.

⁷⁰ Scholars of Biblical studies also acknowledge the difficulty of translating *hoi sphragizomenoi ton nomon*. Whereas Ken PENNER translates the Greek verse as “then those who have sealed the law in order to not learn will be evident,” Jimmy J. M. ROBERTS renders it “then those who are sealed so as not to learn the law will manifest.” PENNER 2020, 83; ROBERTS 2015, 139.

⁷¹ The form *esphragismenoi* appears in two manuscripts of the Septuagint, in the Codex Sinaiticus and the Codex Marchalianus, according to the critical edition of the Septuagint. Ziegler 1983, 152; PENNER 2020, 82.

	<p>Widespread: Then those who have sealed the law in order to not learn will be evident.⁷²</p> <p>Or</p> <p>Less Widespread: Then those who are sealed/seal themselves in order to not learn the law will be evident.</p>	<p>in order not to learn the law (<i>da-l-nāmosā lā nēlpun</i>).⁷³</p>
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One could render *sphragizomenoi* and its variant reading *esphragismenoi* as “being sealed” or “having sealed oneself” based on the fact that *sphragizō* was written in the Middle voice. The Greek Middle voice enables passive (“are sealed”), reflexive (“seal themselves”), and active understandings of sealing.⁷⁴ Moreover, in Greek, it is syntactically possible to begin with the

⁷² The majority of Christian theologians correctly rendered *sphragizomenoi* as “have sealed,” since this meaning is supported by the wider context of the Book of Isaiah and the Old Testament. See e.g., Théodoret de Cyr, *Commentaire sur Isaïe* (1980), 1, 312–313; Cyril of Alexandria, *Commentary on Isaiah* (2008), 1, 193–194. The same understanding of “sealing the law” appears in a fifth-century Palestinian Syriac lectionary. In this lectionary, Isaiah 8:16 reads as follows: Those will know (*yād ‘in hālēn*) who seal the law (*d-ḥātmin l-nāmosā*) in order not to learn it (*d-lā nēlpun yātēh*). Lewis/Gibson 1897, 25. Verses from Isaiah, preserved in this lectionary, originate from various translations of divergent Greek translations of the Hebrew Bible. As Joseph ZIEGLER explains in his critical edition of the Book of Isaiah, according to the Septuagint, this Palestinian Syriac lectionary follows the Hexaplaric text and was in circulation in Palestine, where the Hexapla was dominant. ZIEGLER assumes that the lectionary was likely written for Melkites in the fifth century. ZIEGLER further argues that differences from the Hexapla are predominantly due to the different renderings of translators. ZIEGLER 1983, 52.

⁷³ Ceriani 1874, 176r. This reading of *hoi sphragizomenoi ton nomon* is also preserved in the tenth-century manuscripts of a Georgian translation of Isaiah. The Georgian translation directly follows the word order of the Greek text but interprets the phrase similar to how it is interpreted in the Syro-Hexapla: Then, those become evident who are sealed [in order] the law not to learn (*mashin tskhad ikvnen aghbechdulni igi shjulsa ara stsavlad*). For the Georgian text, see Blake/Brière 1961, 398. The authors of this critical edition consider the Georgian version “mildly or strongly hexaplaric in character.” Ibid., 8.

⁷⁴ In the active understanding of sealing, Christian exegetes connect *sphragizomenoi* with an object *ton nomon* and understand both words together as “have sealed the law.” The active and passive understandings of this grammatical form in regard to *sphragizō* in the Middle voice are supported by the Septuagint. For an understanding of *sphragizō* in the passive, see for instance Revelation 7:4, 5, and 8, employing *esphragismenōn* and *esphragismenoi* and conveying the understanding of “were sealed.” To this end, Daniel 12:9 is especially worth mentioning, given that sealing of the words is rendered with *esphragismenoi* (“for the words are closed up and

object in the accusative and to therefore translate Isaiah 8:16 in such a way that the discussion of sealing is rendered passively: “Then those who are sealed, *the law* in order to not learn, will be evident.”⁷⁵ One could then easily interpret, “those who are sealed in order not to learn the law,” as discussing people whose hearts are closed and who therefore do not learn and follow the law.

Notably, the Syro-Hexapla proposes a variant reading of Isaiah 8:16, “sealed with a seal,” which reinforces the state of being sealed. It is likely that the “law” referenced by the Syro-Hexapla denotes Mosaic Law, given that *nāmosā* is a word usually employed in relation to Mosaic Law. Yet, the context of Isaiah 8 in the Syro-Hexapla does not suffice to determine the meaning of *nāmosā* with certainty. In other two instances, the “law” stands for God’s law or laws more broadly. *Commentary on Isaiah* attributed to John Chrysostom and preserved in Armenian, characterizes those who are sealed as “rebels against the laws” and inhabitants of cities outside of Jerusalem, juxtaposing Isaiah 8:16 against the background of Isaiah 8:

Then, he says those will be evident who are sealed in order to not learn the law (*haynm zhamanaki, ase, haytnestsin vor knqitsen zorens ar i chusanel*).⁷⁶ That is to say, those are evident who rebel against the laws, the inhabitants of the external cities: for as He burned in the furnace, [burned] those who were outside [the furnace], and did not harm those who were within [in the furnace],⁷⁷ the same thing also happened there.⁷⁸

Another *Commentary on Isaiah*, attributed to Basil of Caesaria, first follows the majority interpretation of Isaiah 8:16 but then renders *sphragizomenoi* reflexively as “seal themselves.” The commentary equates “the law” with God’s “words” and “the word of truth” and describes how those who seal themselves do not become Christians:

Then those who seal the law (*hoi sphragizomenoi ton nomon*) in order not to learn shall be manifest: [...] But there are also men who shut up their soul (*apkleiontes [sic] [apokleiontes] heautōn tēn psychēn*)

sealed till the time of the end”). For an understanding of *sphragizō* in the active, despite the fact that it was written in the Middle voice, see for example 2 Corinthians 1:22 and Romans 15:28, using the participle *sphragisamenos* and rendered as “having sealed (the fruit)” and “placed (His) seal (on us).”

⁷⁵ I am thankful to Nestor Kavvadas for responding my inquiry about the syntax of Greek.

⁷⁶ The Latin translation reads as follows: *Tunc, dicit, manifesti erunt qui signatur, ut non discant legem. In Isaiam prophetam interpretatio Sancti Joannis Chrysostomi archiepiscopi Constantinopolitani* 1887, 125.

⁷⁷ This passage invokes Daniel 3:1–30.

⁷⁸ For the Armenian text, see *Yeraneluyn hovhannu voskeberani meknutyun yesayay margarey* 1880, 104; For a Latin translation, see *In Isaiam prophetam interpretatio Sancti Joannis Chrysostomi archiepiscopi Constantinopolitani* 1887, 125. My thanks are due to Natia Dundua and Irma Khositashvili for helping me with Old Armenian.

completely, in order not to receive the word. They as it were tie up (*apodesmountes heautous*) and seal (*sphragizomenoi*) themselves, so that the word of truth may not enter. Those who assimilate themselves to the form of adversary, and do not admit Christ to be formed in them,⁷⁹ who counterfeit the image of the heavenly [man] and rejoice only in the image of the earthy one⁸⁰ are also said to “seal themselves” (*sphragizesthai*).⁸¹

Those who seal themselves are identified as Jews in the subsequent paragraph, and thus, the concept of sealing oneself is employed as part of an anti-Jewish polemic. Sealing in these two *Commentaries on Isaiah* is clearly imbued with Biblical imagery, and allusions are made to numerous Biblical verses. These Christian intertexts share the negative connotation of sealing with the Qur’ān. Yet, the imagery and verses referenced as well as the anti-Jewish rhetoric related to sealing’s occurrence found the Christian intertext(s) are absent from the Qur’ān. One must also highlight two further significant differences between the Qur’ān and its intertexts: those who are sealed are transformed from the Jews to the contemporaries of Muḥammad, and contrary to the Qur’ān, the Christian intertexts do not suggest that God seals the disbelievers. The change of the group who are sealed or seal themselves and the lack of God as the apparent actor in the aforementioned Christian passages, in contrast to the more active role that God plays in the Qur’ān, is reminiscent of 2 Corinthians 3:12–16 and e.g., Q 6:25 and 17:46. Whereas a veil covers the hearts of the Jews (*taḥpitā ‘al lebbhon ramyā* = “a veil covers their hearts”) in 2 Corinthians 3:12–16, God puts coverings on the hearts of the contemporaries of the prophet Muḥammad (*ja‘alnā ‘alā qulūbihim akinnatan* = “We put coverings on their hearts”).

⁷⁹ The phrase “Christ to be formed in them” invokes Galatians 4:19.

⁸⁰ The idea of the images of the heavenly and the earthy men is reminiscent of 1 Corinthians 15:49.

⁸¹ For the Greek text, see Basilius Magnus Caesariensis archiepiscopus, *Commentarius in Isaiam prophetam* (1888), 489 and 492 (paragraph 215); For an English translation, see Basil the Great, *Commentary on the Prophet Isaiah*, trans. Lipatov, 259–260; There are no variant readings of sealing in the relevant paragraph 215 as Volker Drecoll has pointed out to me. Volker Drecoll and Nikolai Lipatov-Chicherin are currently preparing a critical edition of the Greek text at the University of Tübingen. I am grateful to Volker Drecoll for sharing the relevant passage of the forthcoming critical edition with me. For a discussion of a possibility of translating “seal themselves,” see again Basilius Magnus Caesariensis archiepiscopus, *Commentarius in Isaiam prophetam* (1888), 489, n 68.

Conclusion

In this study, I have demonstrated that both the positive and negative connotations of sealing in the Qur'ān originate from Christian interpretations of sealing inspired by Isaiah 8:16 and Daniel 9:24 juxtaposed with key New Testament verses. Whereas the Qur'ānic concept of “seal of the prophets” is especially influenced by the translations that by and large followed the wording of the original Hebrew of Isaiah 8:16 and Daniel 9:24, with slight interpretational revisions, discussion of the sealing of disbelievers' hearts and ears clearly originates from the Septuagint's rendering of Isaiah 8:16. The Book of Isaiah was popular among Christians, often cited and recited due to its messianic character and prophecies which Christians interpreted as foretelling the coming of Christ.⁸² Therefore, it is reasonable to believe that, Isaiah 8:16, commentaries on it, or homilies invoking its wording might have become known within the Qur'ānic milieu and the Arabian Peninsula.

I have shown that the concept of the “seal of the prophets” is prevalent in pre-Islamic Syriac Christian literature, which employs the root *h-t-m*, a Syriac cognate of the Arabic *kh-t-m*, to denote sealing in the sense of confirming, fulfilling, and completing. Importantly, the use of sealing in Syriac literature and the Qur'ān underscores Jesus's and Muḥammad's status as the great prophets who end the list of the prophets who are the recipients of the covenants and “laws” from God. I have also suggested that the notion of sealing of the disbelievers might have entered the Qur'ānic milieu via Syriac, particularly via the Syro-Hexapla, which was widely read in the Syrian Orthodox Church. We should consider these negative connotations of the Qur'ānic sealing in the context of the later Meccan Qur'ān, in which several negative depictions of impairing senses with proven Biblical precursors first appear as part of rhetoric against disbelievers. Still, even if one exercises caution and disregards the Syro-Hexapla due to its possible later dating, the Greek and Armenian *Commentaries on Isaiah* remain as potent Christian intertexts for the Qur'an, intertexts that prove that the concept of the disbelievers' being sealed was in early circulation in the Christian world.

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⁸² DE SOUSA 2021, 245.

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